

IDENTIFICATION AND PREVALENCE OF FUNGAL PATHOGENS ASSOCIATED WITH POSTHARVEST DECAY OF ONION (*ALLIUM CEPA*) IN SELECTED MARKETS OF LOKOJA, KOGI STATE, NIGERIA

¹Festus Olakunle Tawose, ²Gbadebo Barnabas Olukotun, ³Esther Iyadunni Meseke

¹Department of Botany, Faculty of Science, Federal University Lokoja.

festus.tawose@fulokoja.edu.ng

²Department of Food and Industrial Biotechnology, National Biotechnology Research and Development Agency Abuja, Nigeria.

³Department of Botany, Faculty of Science, Federal University Lokoja, Nigeria.

Abstract

Onion (Allium cepa) is a major vegetable crop widely consumed across Nigeria. However, fungal spoilage during storage results in significant postharvest losses. This study investigated the dominant fungal pathogens associated with decaying onion bulbs from five major markets in Lokoja, Kogi State. Twenty-five infected bulbs were collected, and fungal isolates were identified through morphological and cultural characteristics. The study revealed the presence of six fungal genera: Aspergillus, Mucor, Alternaria, Fusarium, Penicillium, and Rhizopus, with Aspergillus sp. being the most prevalent (31%). Pathogenicity tests confirmed Aspergillus sp. as the most virulent, followed by Mucor sp. The findings underscore the need for pre- and postharvest interventions to reduce fungal contamination and associated losses, highlighting the importance of seed treatment, hygienic handling, and awareness creation.

Keywords:

Identification, Prevalence, Fungal pathogens, Postharvest, Decay, Onion.

Introduction

Onion (*Allium cepa* L.) Among the leading vegetable crops in terms of cultivation and consumption across the world, prized for its culinary adaptability, nutritional value, and significant economic impact. Believed to have originated in Central Asia, onions have historically spread across continents and became an integral crop in regions such as ancient Egypt, where they held not only nutritional but also cultural significance (Ochar & Kim, 2023). In Nigeria, onions are an essential part of daily diets and are frequently used for seasoning and flavoring in household and commercial food preparations.

Onion cultivation thrives best in light, sandy soils and in cool, moist climates. Taxonomically, the onion belongs to the kingdom *Plantae*, class *Angiosperm*, order *Asparagales*, family *Amaryllidaceae*, and genus *Allium* (Dorrigiv *et al.*, 2020). Despite its agricultural and economic value, onion production is significantly hampered by various plant pathogens, especially fungi, which affect both field crops and stored bulbs. Common fungal diseases of onion include downy mildew, purple blotch, white rot, basal rot, and neck rot (Shin *et al.*, 2023; Suleiman & Falaiye, 2013). These diseases not only reduce yield but also compromise the quality of onions during storage, limiting their availability for domestic consumption and international trade (Samuel & Ifeanyi, 2015; Petropoulos *et al.*, 2017).

Postharvest spoilage of onions is particularly concerning in tropical climates, where ambient storage conditions (24–32°C and variable relative humidity) create an environment conducive to fungal growth (Nakra *et al.*, 2025). Notable spoilage organisms include *Fusarium spp.*, *Botrytis spp.*, and *Aspergillus niger*, which are commonly associated with basal rot, neck rot, and black mold disease (Muhie, 2022). Among these, *Aspergillus niger* is particularly prevalent, known for its ability to persist in the soil and infect bulbs during and after harvest. Its spoilage potential is further compounded by the risk of mycotoxin production, posing significant health hazards (Falola & Achem, 2017).

In regions like Kogi State, Nigeria, onion farming plays a critical role in local economies. However, the widespread occurrence of postharvest spoilage caused by fungal pathogens undermines production efficiency and profitability. Despite the importance of onions and the challenges posed by fungal diseases, there is a scarcity of localized studies identifying the dominant fungal pathogens responsible for storage decay. A clearer understanding of these spoilage organisms is essential to developing effective postharvest management strategies.

This study aims to investigate the predominant fungal pathogens associated with postharvest decay of onion bulbs in Kogi State, with the goal of informing control strategies and reducing postharvest losses. Such information is vital for improving onion quality, enhancing food safety, and promoting sustainable agricultural practices.

Statement of Research Problem

Fungal contamination during harvesting, handling, transportation, and storage under ambient tropical conditions (24–32°C) significantly contributes to onion spoilage in Nigeria (Patil *et al.*, 2024). *Aspergillus niger*, the causative agent of black mold, thrives under such conditions, leading to rot and mycotoxin production (Navale, *et al.*, 2021). The extent of contamination during storage poses health risks and economic setbacks, especially for farmers and marketers (Falola and Achem, 2017).

Justification

Onion is indispensable in Nigerian cuisine and plays a vital role in the livelihood of farmers and traders. However, its perishability due to fungal pathogens underlines the need for proactive disease management. A comprehensive understanding of the fungi responsible for spoilage is necessary to develop postharvest control measures. Despite the onion's economic significance, few studies have addressed specific fungal agents in Kogi State, necessitating this research.

Aim

To identify and determine the dominant fungal pathogens of decaying onion bulbs from selected markets in Lokoja, Kogi State, Nigeria.

Objectives

1. To isolate and identify dominant fungi associated with onion bulb decay in the study areas.
2. To determine the prevalence of fungal association.
3. To evaluate the pathogenicity of the isolated fungi.
4. To create awareness of the health implications of the associated fungi.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area and Sample Collection Sites

The study was carried out in Lokoja, the capital of Kogi State, Nigeria. Onion samples were obtained from five major retail markets within the Lokoja metropolis: Zango-Daji, Otokiti, Zone 8, Old Market, and Felele Market. These markets were selected due to their high customer traffic and easy accessibility to the public,

Sample Collection

A total of 25 onion bulbs showing visible signs of spoilage or deterioration were collected five samples from each market. The visibly infected bulbs were individually placed in sterile polythene bags, labeled according to market of origin, and transported under hygienic conditions to the laboratory at Kogi State Polytechnic, Lokoja, for microbiological analysis.

Sterilization of Equipment and Media Preparation

Glassware was sterilized in oven at 160 °C for 2 hours, following the method of Oniah and Tawose (2018). Work surfaces were disinfected with 70% ethanol and left undisturbed for 30 minutes. The inoculating needle and cork borer were flame-sterilized using a spirit lamp before and after each use. The inoculating needle and cork borer were flame-sterilized using a spirit lamp before and after each use. The medium was then plated and allowed to solidify at room temperature prior to inoculation.

Isolation of Fungal Pathogens

The protocol described by Kikulwe et al. (2018) was followed for fungal isolation. Infected sections of onion bulbs were surface sterilized using 1% sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) solution for 2 minutes, then rinsed three times with sterile distilled water to remove residual disinfectant. Approximately 1 g of the infected tissue was aseptically macerated and homogenized in 9 mL of sterile peptone water. The suspension was thoroughly mixed, and a 1 mL aliquot was subjected to tenfold serial dilutions up to 10^{-6} . From the 10^{-2} and 10^{-4} dilutions, 0.1 mL was inoculated onto Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) plates and incubated at 28 °C for 5 days. Distinct fungal colonies that emerged were sub-cultured onto fresh PDA to obtain pure isolates for further analysis

Microscopic Identification of Fungi

Pure fungal cultures were examined morphologically. A sterile inoculating needle was used to transfer a small portion of each colony onto a clean glass slide. A drop of lactophenol cotton blue stain was added, and the preparation was covered with a cover slip. The slide was briefly passed over a Bunsen flame to remove air bubbles and then examined under a compound microscope using 10× and 100× objectives. Fungal identification was based on colony morphology and microscopic characteristics and compared with standard taxonomic keys and relevant literature.

Pathogenicity Test

The pathogenicity test procedure of Pérez-Hernández, *et al.*, (2020) was followed with slight modifications. The pathogenicity of isolated fungal strains was confirmed using healthy onion bulbs. Five uninfected bulbs were cleaned and surface-sterilized with 70% ethanol. With a 5mm diameter cork borer, wounds were inflicted on the surface of each bulb. A portion of the pure fungal culture was introduced into the wound using a sterile inoculating needle. Inoculated wounds were sealed with sterile paraffin to prevent contamination, labeled accordingly, and kept at 30 °C for 7 days. Following incubation, symptoms were assessed, and the fungi were re-isolated from the infected tissues to confirm Koch's postulates. For the control experiment, bulbs were wounded but not inoculated to rule out abiotic factors.

Results

Twenty-five (25) samples of rotten tissues of some onion bulbs collected from different markets in Lokoja Metropolis in Kogi State were analyzed using mycological methods. The filamentous fungi genera that were isolated and studied from the respective market sites includes *Aspergillus* sp., *Mucor* sp., *Alternaria* sp., *Fusarium* sp., *Penicillium* sp., and *Rhizopus* sp. All the fungi genera were present at Zone 8 and Felele markets whereas *Alternaria* sp. and *Fusarium* sp. were not isolated from Otokiti Markets (Table 1).

Table 1: Frequency of Pathogenic Fungal Isolates in Onions from Different Locations

Site (Market)	Fungi Association					
	<i>Asperg. sp.</i>	<i>Altern. sp.</i>	<i>Fusar. sp.</i>	<i>Penici. sp.</i>	<i>Mucor sp.</i>	<i>Rhiz. sp.</i>
Otokiti	+	-	-	+	+	+
Zone 8	+	+	+	+	+	+
Old-Market	+	+	+	-	+	+
Felele Market	+	+	+	+	+	+
Zango-Daji	+	+	-	+	+	+

Table 2 shows percentage frequency of fungal pathogens isolated from rotten onion bulbs collected from the study sites. *Aspergillus* sp. had the highest occurrence (31%), followed by *Mucor* sp., while *Fusarium* sp. had the lowest (05%).

Table 2: Occurrence of Fungal Pathogens in Rotten Onions from the Studied Areas

Fungi	Incidence (%)
<i>Aspergillus</i> sp.	31
<i>Mucor</i> sp.	24
<i>Alternaria</i> sp.	09
<i>Fusarium</i> sp.	05
<i>Penicillium</i> sp.	16
<i>Rhizopus</i> sp.	15

Table 3: The Pathogenicity of the Isolated Fungi

Fungal Infection	(mm)
<i>Aspergillus</i> sp.	23
<i>Mucor</i> sp.	18
<i>Alternaria</i> sp.	09
<i>Fusarium</i> sp.	17
<i>Penicillium</i> sp.	16
<i>Rhizopus</i> sp.	15

Table 3 shows the pathogenicity effects of the respective fungal culture. *Fusarium* sp. had the highest diameter (23mm) of infection followed by *Penicillium* sp. (16mm). *Alternaria* sp. had the lowest of 05mm.

DISCUSSION

This study was conducted to assess the fungal species associated with rotting onion bulbs collected from various markets across the Lokoja metropolis in Kogi State, Nigeria. The analysis revealed six fungal genera: *Aspergillus* sp., *Mucor* sp., *Alternaria* sp., *Fusarium* sp., *Penicillium* sp., and *Rhizopus* sp. These findings are consistent with previous studies such as those by Tawose et al. (2019) and Günaçtı (2023), who reported the presence of *Aspergillus niger*, *Fusarium* sp., *Sclerotium cepivorum*, *Rhizopus stolonifer*, *Scopulariopsis brevicaulis*, *Candida tropicalis*, and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* in decaying vegetables. Similarly, Patil et al. (2024) identified *Aspergillus* sp., *Fusarium* sp., and *Rhizopus* sp. in deteriorating onions, though *C. tropicalis* and *S. cerevisiae* were not detected in their study.

Among the isolated fungi, *Aspergillus niger* was the most frequently encountered, constituting approximately 31% of the total isolates. This dominance is consistent with the work of Suleiman and Falaiye (2015). Their findings revealed *A. niger* to be the dominant and most virulent fungal pathogen. *A. niger* is widely recognized as a primary etiological agent responsible for black mold disease in onions, particularly during storage. Its high virulence and prevalence underscore its significant role in postharvest losses, especially under suboptimal storage conditions.

Other fungi isolated in this study—*Penicillium*, *Alternaria*, *Rhizopus*, and *Mucor*—have also been reported in the literature as causative agents of onion bulb rot. These pathogens can induce severe tissue decay, particularly under conditions of high humidity and mechanical

damage to the bulbs. According to previous studies, fungi such as *Alternaria* and *Penicillium* contribute to 15–30% losses in onion storage depending on the variety and storage condition. Such economic losses are detrimental to the livelihood of farmers and vendors, especially in regions where onion cultivation is a key agricultural activity.

This study found a relatively high incidence rate of onion rot—approximately 49.7%—in the sampled markets, indicating a major concern for food security and market sustainability. This high percentage suggests that fungal spoilage poses a significant threat to onion marketers and underscores the need for effective preventive and management strategies. Notably, *Aspergillus* sp., *Mucor* sp., and *Rhizopus* sp. were consistently isolated from all markets examined. This widespread distribution aligns with reports by Muhie (2022), who described these fungi as ubiquitous in nature and frequently isolated from a range of agricultural produce. Their adaptability and persistence may explain their high frequency of occurrence in stored onions.

The ubiquitous nature of these fungi and their ability to persist in diverse environments increase the risk of infection during storage, particularly when bulbs are not properly handled. Wounding during harvesting, transportation, and marketing creates entry points for fungal propagules, which subsequently colonize the nutrient-rich tissue and lead to varying degrees of decay. Therefore, postharvest handling practices play a critical role in either facilitating or preventing fungal invasion and spoilage.

Furthermore, the widespread presence of these fungi in market samples implies a potential field-to-storage continuum in disease transmission. The fungi may originate from infected seeds or soil and establish themselves during crop development, remaining latent until harvest and then proliferating under conducive storage conditions. This highlights the importance of adopting an integrated approach to fungal disease management. Implementing practices such as selecting clean, disease-free seeds, treating seeds with the right chemicals before planting, and adhering to Good Agricultural Practices (GAP) during harvesting and postharvest handling is crucial for disrupting the disease cycle.

Conclusion

This study has demonstrated that over 50% of onion spoilage in the sampled markets was associated with infections by *Aspergillus* sp., with this and other fungal species present in over 82% of the collected samples. These findings confirm the critical role of fungal pathogens in postharvest losses of onion bulbs. The knowledge gained from this study is vital for designing effective control strategies. Preventive strategies, including the use of disease-free seeds, timely and appropriate application of fungicides, and careful handling of onion bulbs during harvesting and postharvest processes, are essential to reduce both field infections and storage-related spoilage. Implementing such practices will not only enhance onion shelf-life and market value but also contribute to reducing economic losses for farmers and traders within the Lokoja metropolis and similar agro-ecological zones.

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